

AGE- AND SEASON-MEDIATED CHANGES IN DNA METHYLATION AND EXPRESSION PATTERNS OF SIRTUINS IN GILTHEAD SEA BREAM *Sparus aurata*

Paula Simó-Mirabet*, Erick Perera, Josep Alvar Caldach-Giner, Jaume Pérez-Sánchez

Nutrigenomics and Fish Growth Endocrinology Group, Institute of Aquaculture Torre de la Sal, IATS-CSIC, 12595 Ribera de Cabanes s/n, Castelloñ, Spain

E-mail: paula.simo@csic.es

Introduction

Sirtuins (SIRT) are a conserved family of enzymes that couple protein deacetylation of histone and non-histone substrates with the energy status of the cell via the cellular NAD⁺/NADH ratio. This protein family has been largely conserved through evolution, and the SIRT counterparts of higher vertebrates have been identified and molecularly characterized in gilthead sea bream (Simó-Mirabet et al., 2017). Transcriptional studies have also revealed a ubiquitous *sirt* gene expression that is tissue-specific for each *sirt* and highly dependent on feed intake and growth potentiality (Simó-Mirabet et al., 2017, 2018). This agrees with an epigenetic role of SIRT related with developmental, differentiation and genome environment interactions. Nevertheless, there are few studies assessing the DNA methylation pattern of SIRT promoters, and the aim of this study was to determine if changes of *sirt* gene expression in liver and white skeletal muscle of one- and three-year old fish during winter and summer are due, at least in part, to changes in DNA methylation of *sirt* promoters. The study also included the gene expression profiling of markers of oxidative metabolism (*cs*, *cpt1a*, *pgc1a*) and mitochondrial respiration uncoupling (*ucp1*, *ucp3*).

Materials and methods

The exon-intron organization of the seven gilthead seabream *sirts* was determined by blat searches in our genomic gilthead sea bream database (<http://nutrigrp-iats.org/seabreamdb>). This *in silico* analysis included predictions of transcription start sites (TSS), core promoter regions, transcription factor binding sites (TFBS) and CpG islands (CGIs). For transcriptional and DNA methylation assays, tissue portions of liver and white skeletal muscle were processed for RNA and DNA extraction in fish of two class of age (+1, +3) at two different times (winter, February 2018; summer, June 2018). DNA methylation was examined by bisulfite conversion and pyrosequencing of CGIs close to TSS of *sirt1* (22 CpG sites) and *sirt3* (4 CpG sites). Gene expression patterns of *sirt1-7* in addition to that of *cs*, *cpt1a*, *pgc1a*, *ucp1*, and *ucp3* were analyzed by a PCR-array designed for the simultaneous gene expression profiling of all genes in the analyzed tissues.

Results

The number and length of exons-introns are highly conserved for each *sirt* variant through the evolution, despite of the variable length of introns across species (humans/sea bream/zebrafish) (Fig. 1A). Clear CGIs were only found at the 5'-flanking region of *sirt1* and *sirt3* (Fig. 1B). The analyzed CpG sites of *sirt3* remained highly hypomethylated regardless of age, season and tissue. By contrast, the methylation level of the 22 analyzed CpG sites of *sirt1* varied with age in skeletal muscle. Thus, in comparison to age +3, young fish (+1) sampled in summer, but not in winter, showed a two-fold increase in the methylation level of CpG sites close to TSS, reaching values close to 4% in the first four CpG sites. This feature was accompanied by a decreased expression of *sirt1*, which reduced the difference of expression between fish of the age class +1 and +3 when comparisons are made in summer. This was especially evident at the position CpG3, as it was evidenced by correlation analysis of *sirt1* gene expression and methylation level (Pearson Correlation Coefficient = -0.7; P = 0.007) (Fig. 1D). Intriguingly, skeletal muscle also appeared more responsive than liver to changes in *sirt* gene expression with a statistically significant interaction of age and season for *sirt1*, 4, 5 and 7, which was extensive to *cs* and *cpt1a*. This was reinforced by discriminant analysis (PLS-DA), which identified *cs*, *cpt1a* and *ucp1* as the most important variable loads in liver, whereas *sirts* contribute to better discriminate the energy status of skeletal muscle.

Discussion and conclusions

The presence of CGIs close to TSS did not match well with the level of *sirt* gene expression (*sirt5*>*sirt2*>*sirt1*>*sirt 3/4/6/7*). However, the overall hypomethylation of *sirt1* and *sirt3* CGIs would provide a transcriptionally permissive state that ensures their basal expression in relation with their central role in mitochondrial and intermediary metabolism. Moreover, methylation changes at specific CpG positions of *sirt1* promoter were tissue-specific (e.g. skeletal muscle) in response to a particular energy situation (e.g. summer). These results corroborate the high value of *sirts* as energy sensors through life cycle. This is the first study analyzing the DNA methylation at CpG islands located at the promoter region of *sirts* genes in a marine fish, and provide new insights into *sirt* regulation as key markers of energy status.

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Fig.1. A) Gene structure of GSB *sirt1*. Non-coding exons: white boxes, coding exons: black boxes, introns: lines. B) CGIs of *sirt1* (yellow). Numbers indicate position respect to the ATG. C) Effects of age (+1, black, +3, grey) on DNA-methylation in WSM. D) Correlation of CpG3 methylation and *sirt1* expression in WSM during summer.

References

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